

GENDER EQUALITY ISSUES IN EDUCATION SYSTEM

Mohlaroyim Keldiyorova Uchqun qizi

Kimyo International University in Samarkand, English Language department,
e-mail: Keldiyarovamohlaroyim@gmail.com
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Science and technology are at the heart of the development of human well-being and the long-term progress of civilization, which should be reflected in a serious increase in public investment in education. Studies show that in all countries there are no discriminatory laws restricting the education or professional activities of women, including young ones. However, in real life, boys and girls have different opportunities in acquiring education and obtaining decent professional employment in the modern labor market.

This thesis is devoted to the analysis of gender differences in access to different levels of general and vocational education.

Despite the fact that the legislation of the countries of Central Asia and the CIS does not contain norms allowing to give preference to any gender in access to education, in real life the gender composition of students is quite asymmetric.

Considering the problem of the ratio of boys and girls among secondary school students, it should be borne in mind that in all Central Asian countries, the gender problems of the primary and basic levels of general education differ significantly from the gender problems in high school.

In the countries of Central Asia, as in the rest of the CIS countries, there are virtually no gender differences in the composition of students at the primary and basic levels of secondary schools. At these levels of education for boys, although the proportion of girls exceeds somewhat, but these differences mainly reflect only differences in the proportion of boys and girls in the corresponding age group.

Statistics show that in all countries of the region, the proportion of girls among students of primary vocational education institutions, although significantly different, is everywhere less than boys. At the same time, studies show that there is no single reason for the existence of such a situation for all countries. In a number of countries (such as Russia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan), gender asymmetry in the composition of students is associated with differences in the strategy of obtaining vocational education that has developed between men and women. Women in these countries are striving to obtain a higher and higher level of education, and primary vocational education today is unattractive for them. Men are increasingly limited to lower levels of vocational education.

In other countries (Uzbekistan and Tajikistan), the modest proportion of girls among vocational school students is explained by the widespread prevalence of traditional gender roles and gender discrimination in access to education by families. Girls from poor families are increasingly being persuaded to marry early, and with a lack of funds, families prefer to pay for the education of their sons rather than their daughters. In this situation, primary vocational education is quite attractive for girls today.

At the second level of vocational education - in the system of secondary special education - the proportion of girls among students in all countries is higher than in the system of primary vocational education, and it everywhere exceeds the corresponding proportion of boys. In many countries, this level of professional education is currently the most feminized.

The third level of professional education - higher education - is not so vividly feminized, assessing the level of representation of women among university students, two groups of countries can be distinguished. Firstly, these are countries in which the proportion of women among students is significantly higher than the corresponding proportion of men, and the implementation of a strategy for women to obtain the highest level of vocational education has already led (or will lead in the foreseeable future) to a higher level of their education compared to men. Secondly, these are countries in which the maintenance of traditional gender roles contributes to the preservation of traditional gender asymmetry in the level of education of the population.

It is necessary to realize that the manifestation of gender inequality in the process of development itself is unacceptable, and development without education is unthinkable. That is why a smart gender policy is needed, first of all in university education.

The question arises: what are the factors acting as a barrier to achieving gender equality in society? It is clear that there is a whole complex of them: from socio-economic to socio-political and cultural-psychological, with its own specifics and concrete historical tradition.

In fact, women in the world accounted for a slightly larger share — 53% — of graduates with bachelor's and master's degrees. The data show that the rates of exclusion and the associated gender gaps tend to grow in line with higher levels of education in many regions and countries. For example, more women currently earn bachelor's degrees worldwide than men, but the persistence of gender inequality prevents women from achieving the highest level of education, and they currently make up less than 30% of researchers.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that it is important to use the opportunity to take a position for women and girls in the education system and break stereotypes. It is clear that bridging the gender gap in education is vital. The emphasis on the quality of education and the focus on a sound strategy is something that can improve the academic performance and learning of all children, and therefore will contribute to achieving gender equality.

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